

THE HISTORY OF THE FORMATION OF ENVIRONMENTAL EDUCATION AND ITS SIGNIFICANCE IN THE PUBLIC CONSCIOUSNESS

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Abstract: the improvement of the ecological culture of the population and society is possible due to the effective introduction of a system of continuous environmental education in our country. The fact is that without the formation of ecological consciousness and culture among the population, primarily among students and students studying in the system of continuing education, it is impossible to solve problems with any means spent on ecology and environmental protection. The relevance of environmental education is determined by the nature of our country, its ecosystems, the need to protect the environment from instability and disruption, increase the ecological culture of the population, contribute to these very serious, vital issues by all segments of the population, especially young people.

Keywords: ecology, ecological culture, ecological consciousness, nature, globalization.

ИСТОРИЯ СТАНОВЛЕНИЯ ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ И ЕГО ЗНАЧЕНИЕ В ОБЩЕСТВЕННОМ СОЗНАНИИ

Аннотация: повышение экологической культуры населения и общества возможно благодаря эффективному внедрению системы непрерывного экологического образования в нашей стране. Дело в том, что без формирования экологического сознания и культуры у населения, в первую очередь у школьников и студенток, обучающихся в системе непрерывного образования, невозможно решить проблемы любыми средствами, затраченными на экологию и охрану окружающей среды. Актуальность экологического образования определяется природой нашей страны, ее экосистемами, необходимостью защищать окружающую среду от нестабильности и разрушений, повышать экологическую культуру населения, способствовать решению этих очень серьезных, жизненно важных вопросов всеми слоями населения, особенно молодежью.

Ключевые слова: экология, экологическая культура, экологическое сознание, природа, глобализация.

INTRODUCTION

Ecological knowledge in the Republic of Uzbekistan has developed intensively and in a peculiar way. According to a number of authors, our region has developed a rich, unique set of traditions of dialogue between nature and man, nature and society. One of the most characteristic features of this dialogue is a respectful, respectful attitude towards the earth. The cult of the native land has always been present in the traditional consciousness. There are many such phrases in the national speech: the native land, the mother of cheese, the motherland, etc. These features - the constant dialogue of man with nature, the indissoluble connection of the people with the earth - are reproduced and comprehended in Uzbek science.

The development of the tradition of dialogue between society and nature quite naturally led to the idea of coevolution - the harmonious development of society and the biosphere on the basis of the ecological imperative - universal responsibility for the fate of the planet of all peoples of the world[1].

The formation of domestic environmental education was also promoted by the global environmental movement.

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

The main goal of ecological education is the formation of ecological culture, responsible attitude of the individual to nature, the development of ecological consciousness and thinking. Environmental education - a continuous process of learning, upbringing and personal development. On the basis of Environmental Education, a person is indifferent to the environmental teaching, upbringing and culture of the individual, to the correct and rational way of preserving nature and its wealth, in economical use, to devote practical work to solving environmental problems.

Ecologization of pedagogical theory and educational practice is considered as an indispensable part of any educational systems. Now an attempt is being made to create an educational complex in which continuous environmental education and upbringing would be carried out, representing the system: school - college (lyceum) – pedagogical university - institute for advanced training of educational workers.

The purpose of higher pedagogical education is the formation of a comprehensively developed, socially mature personality, the training of a qualified teacher. The subordinate goal of pedagogical education is the formation of readiness for optimal interaction with nature[2].

To solve this problem, the following groups of factors should be taken into account when implementing environmental education of pedagogical university students:

- factors arising from the public need to optimize the teacher's interaction with the natural environment and the peculiarities of socio-ecological experience;
- factors arising from the conditions of university teacher training;
- factors arising from the pedagogical system "teacher -student".

The main principles of building the content of environmental education of pedagogical university students are:

- the principle of orientation of the content of environmental education to prepare teachers for their own optimal interaction with nature, for effective environmental education of schoolchildren and students, for environmental education of the population;

- the principle of orientation of the content of environmental education to the formation of a comprehensively developed personality and a highly qualified specialist teacher;
- the principle of reflecting elements of socio-ecological experience in the content of environmental education: environmental emotional and value relations, activities, knowledge;
- the principle of conformity of the structure of the content of environmental education to the structure of the pedagogical process of the pedagogical university.

RESEARCH RESULTS

The purpose of this study was to develop the theoretical foundations for optimizing the educational process, stimulating the student's withdrawal to a high level of readiness for the implementation of environmental education in an educational institution and outside it. This goal was realized by such tasks as the development of a concept for building a system of environmental education of students in a pedagogical university, the development of an integrated interdisciplinary content of environmental education in a pedagogical university and a number of other tasks[3]. In the development of this system, researchers recognized the special role of the pedagogical university. It is in the pedagogical university that the personnel engaged in environmental education of students are trained. The decision on the formation of the ecological culture of future citizens of the country depends on the level of readiness of a graduate of a pedagogical university for environmental education and upbringing of a student.

Such features of higher education as:

- universality of curricula;
- the variety of educational directions in which graduates will work;
- increased (in comparison with other categories of universities) consistency of the entire process of education, stimulate the implementation of environmental education in it. They make it possible to fully realize the interdisciplinary potential of environmental education.

The structure-forming component is the motivational-value component, which assumes a hierarchical system of motives for ecological and pedagogical activity, as well as value-based ecological, pedagogical orientations of the teacher.

Readiness for pedagogical activity largely determines the essence of a teacher's readiness for ecological and pedagogical activity.

DISCUSSION

The teacher's readiness for ecological and pedagogical activity is an integral education, an integrative property of his personality, a system of its qualities that ensure the creation of conditions for the development of ecological culture of students, the formation of their responsible attitude to nature. This readiness determines whether a teacher has a system of ecological and pedagogical knowledge and skills, an image of the structure of ecological and pedagogical actions, operations and a constant focus of consciousness on their implementation; it includes installations for awareness of ecological and pedagogical goals and objectives, models of probable behavior for their implementation, determination of conditions, means, technologies of ecological and pedagogical activity, assessment of their capabilities in their relation to the upcoming difficulties and the need to achieve a certain result in the development of ecological culture of students.

The realization of the goal of pedagogical education - the formation of a teacher-the subject of his professional activity, his life strategy, self-development, readiness for pedagogical (including ecological and pedagogical) activities - requires a detailed technological justification of the specialist training process.

The higher school is designed to make the most significant contribution to the process of environmental education and education of future specialists.

At the same time, it should be noted that the level of environmental knowledge of students of pedagogical institutes is insufficient for the organization of effective work on environmental education of students of secondary schools and vocational schools. This disadvantage is typical for many universities. In most pedagogical universities, students' participation in environmental activities is limited at best to preparing and writing sections on nature conservation in their thesis. Even at the level of higher education, young people are often more inclined to fix negative manifestations of human interference in the environment than to try to take the initiative and prevent them. Only a few university graduates, as observations have shown, are able to correctly predict the possible consequences of human impact on the natural environment. In this regard, it should be added that, despite the increasing role of environmental education, there is a decrease in attention to ecology as a separate course.

Many scientists (L.Khudorberdiev, M.Mirboboev, S.Salokhitdinov, S.N.Glazachev, V.I.Danilchuk, N.M.Mamedov, A.D.Ursul and others) write about the need to develop the above trends. Developing the ideas of advanced education, it is noted that it is advisable to introduce noospheric and futurological sections in the program of each educational institution. This is also due to the development of projects of a prognostic orientation. Due to the development of science in the XXI century, a university graduate will be ready for life only if he has a stock of predictive knowledge.

A series of numerous publications on our research has become a kind of result of the modern history of the formation of the theory and practice of ecological and pedagogical teacher training. S.N.Glazachev's research presents an anthology of ecological and pedagogical research over the past 30 years through the prism of the formation of one scientific school. The main conclusion is a deep awareness of the new eco-humanitarian educational paradigm, the ecological culture of the teacher.

CONCLUSION

Summing up a brief summary of the formation and development of ecological and pedagogical teacher training, we will highlight three main stages of this process:

- single-subject (late 1960s - 1970s);
- system-subject (1980s - mid-1990s);
- ecohumanitarian (since the late 1990s) (stages of the formation of the ecological culture of the teacher.)

At the last stage, a new goal was formulated for the teacher: to form an ecological culture, harmonizing the freedom and responsibility of the individual. At the same time, the personality of the teacher, his ecological and pedagogical culture will play an increasing role in the modern socio-cultural process.

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